

Recent trend in Bio-fortified wheat production-A review

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Abstract

The daily dietary recommendation is different for both men and women; women's require 8 mg/day zinc while men requires 11 mg/day. Daily meal does not have these micro-nutrition in the diet therefore, it should be supplied from outside source. Therefore, Biofortified wheat is an best option where, More than 2 million people are suffering from malnutrition (FAO, 2016). There are various products of cereals such as Flour from cereals is used for making bread & other products for breakfast cereals, as pasta, snack foods, dry mixes, cakes, pastries, and tortillas. If more bio-fortified cereals can be grown it could enhance the nutritional value of the food as well as sales. Some of the major players in the Indian breakfast cereals market are Kellogg Co., Nestle, PepsiCo, Baggry's India Ltd and Marico. Kellogg's frootloops, Kellogg's rasin bran, Quaker, Wheaties, Nestle fitness and private brands using such products. As per WHO recommendations now Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI) has make it policy for wide food fortification program and now. Common staple foods such as wheat flour, rice, edible oil, and milk have been selected as food vehicle for different micronutrient fortifications.

Keywords: Bio-fortified wheat, FSSAI, bran, malnutrition, breakfast, Folic acid, Thiamine

1.1 Introduction:

Bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is the second most important food crop worldwide after rice. There are various reports of bio-fortified wheat that has been reported in past few year which are rich in zinc (Cardoso et al., 2018; Velu et al., 2015; Zia et al., 2020).

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) is one of the most important food crops globally which provides one-third of the total protein requirements of the populations (Shewry, 2009). It has a protein content ranging from 7 to 15% and plays a vital role in the human diet (Ciclitira & Ellis, 1987). Wheat proteins are generally rich in glutamic acid (Glu) and prolines (Pro), the functional amino acids in extensible dough formation. Protein content along with the amino acid composition determine the nutritional quality of wheat grains (Joye, 2019). The amino acid composition of wheat is not balanced and lacks the adequate amounts of EAA like Lys, Thr, and Met (Jiang, Tian, Zhi, & Zhang, 2008). Processing of wheat into different products results in further depletion of its amino acid contents. With the modern popularization concept of a healthy diet, people are becoming more concerned about health and nutrition (Garg et al., 2018). Recently, colored wheat has gained lots of attentions due to

its health beneficial properties (Gupta, Meghwal, & Prabhakar, 2021; Saini).

Different colors of anthocyanin bio-fortified wheat viz., purple, blue and black depend upon the types and position of anthocyanins in wheat layers (Garg et al., 2016). The purple color is due to localization of anthocyanins in the pericarp layer, blue in the aleurone layer, while, black is combination of the two.

Recent publications have characterized anthocyanins and other nutrients from colored wheat, studied origin and genetics of grain color, developed high yielding regionally adapted germplasm, studied the effect of genotype and environment on anthocyanin accumulation, developed different products, studied the effect of cooking on the stability of anthocyanins and their antioxidant activity and effect of abiotic stresses (Lachman, Martinek, Kotikov, Ors, & Sulc, 2017; Mbarki et al., 2018; Paznocht et al., 2018).

Several studies have reported its grass, sprouts, whole plant and seeds of colored wheat for their anti-inflammatory activity, antimicrobial activity, and other human health benefits including positive effects on neurodegenerative disorders, high-fat diet-induced

derangements like body weight gain, blood cholesterol and glucose and diabetes (Gupta et al., 2021; Mbarki et al., 2018; Paznocht et al., 2018; Saini et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2018, 2020, 2021; Sytar, Bořsko, Živčák, Brestic, & Smetanska, 2018). Due to the growing trend towards nutrition-rich foods, nutritional profiling of these designer crops along with their suitability for the production of high-quality end products has become utmost important. Presently, little is known about the nutritional background of colored wheat grains particularly their amino acid profile (Tian, Chen, & Wei, 2018). Hence, the current study was designed to evaluate the profile of amino acids in flours and chapatti samples of black, blue and purple colored anthocyanin biofortified wheat developed at National Agri-Food Biotechnology Institute (NABI), Punjab, India (Garg et al., 2016). The effect of cooking upon the amino acid content of colored wheat chapatti samples in comparison to white wheat chapattis was also evaluated as anthocyanins are reported to reduce protein degradation in food products upon heating (Oancea, Aprodu, Rapeanu, Bahrim, & Stanciu, 2017). This would be the first study reporting the effect of cooking on amino acid content of anthocyanin rich colored wheat chapattis. Such information could be useful in assessing the quality of diets to meet nutritional requirements of people, particularly of South Asian countries who mainly consume wheat in the form of chapattis.

Zinc deficiency has resulted in various consequences in Asian countries specially India and Pakistan. Therefore, to cop up with major mineral deficiency such as "Iron" and "Zinc" by the plant breeders and agronomist. But real question is that if Bio-fortified wheat has been successfully completed mission of coping with malnutrition. Assessment of release of "Zn" has been done on what variety *Triticum aestivum* L. var. Zincol-2016 (Zia et al., 2020). Mostly, fortification done via fertilizer added in excess zinc (Cardoso et al., 2018) but also there is report of genetic modification technique by which Zinc bio-fortification has been done. In this regard X-ray analysis & QTL mapping has been prove to be very useful tool to detect trace of metal present in wheat flour (Cardoso et al., 2018) (Crespo-Herrera, Govindan, Stangoulis, Hao, & Singh, 2017). WHO started fortified wheat since 2011 and has permitted to add many other components such as Vit A, (https://documents.wfp.org/stellent/groups/public/documents/manual_guide_proced/wfp251105.pdf)

Table 1: Micronutrient rate and chemical form (source WHO public manual available at www.wfo.org)

Vitamin A	1.0 mg/kg	Dry vitamin A palmitate
250 n.s		
Vitamin B1	4.4 mg/kg	Thiamine mononitrate
Vitamin B2	2.6 mg/kg	Riboflavin
Vitamin B3	35.0 mg/kg	Nicotinamide
Folic acid	1.0 mg/kg	Folic acid
Vitamin B 12	0.008 mg/kg	Cyancobalamin
Iron	15 mg/kg	NaFeEDTA
Zinc	30 mg/kg	Zinc oxide.

As per latest report fortified wheat now has been used by Big firms like ITC, HUL & Cargill to fortify wheat flour. (<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com>). Market leaders like the ITC, General Mills, Hindustan Unilever, Patanjali, and Cargill has started fortification of their flagship brands of wheat flour (atta) such as Aashirwaad, Pillsbury, Annapurna, Patanjali and Nature Fresh respectively," the FSSAI. These fortification of wheat is done in aim to cop-up with malnutrition and undernourished people which is more than 50% in Africa and around 15% in India and on around 50% in women's. According to FSSI report folic acid amalgamation is essential to absorb "Fe" in the body and also cost not more than one rupees per kg while they can save more than Rs 25 on prevention by medicine.

Average levels of nutrients to consider adding to fortified wheat flour based on extraction, fortification compound and estimated per capita flour availability.						
Nutrient	Flour Extraction rate	Compound	Level of nutrient to be added in parts per million (ppm) by estimated average per capita wheat flour availability (g/day) ^a			
			<75 ^b g/day	75-149 g/day	150-300 g/day	>300 g/day
Iron	Low	NaFeEDTA	40	40	20	15
		Ferrous Sulfate	60	60	30	20
		Ferrous Fumarate	60	60	30	20
		Electrolytic Iron	NR ^c	NR ^c	60	40
	High	NaFeEDTA	40	40	20	15
Folic acid	Low or high	Folic Acid	5	2.6	1.3	1
Vitamin B12	Low or high	Cyanocobalamin	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.008
Vitamin A	Low or high	Vitamin A Palmitate	5.9	3	1.5	1
Zinc ^d	Low	Zinc Oxide	95	55	40	30
	High	Zinc Oxide	100	100	80	70

a. These estimated levels consider only wheat flour as main fortification vehicle in a public health program. If other mass-fortification programs with other food vehicles are implemented effectively, these suggested fortification levels may need to be adjusted downwards as needed.

b. Estimated per capita consumption of <75 g/day does not allow for addition of sufficient level of fortificant to cover micronutrients needs for women of childbearing age. Fortification of additional food vehicles and other interventions should be considered.

c. NR = Not Recommended because very high levels of electrolytic iron needed could negatively affect sensory

properties of fortified flour.

d. These amounts of zinc fortification assume 5 mg zinc intake and no additional phytate intake from other dietary sources.

* This is an extract from the relevant guidance document (1). Additional guidance information can be found in this document.

Antioxidant status in Bio-fortified wheat

According to latest work done order of antioxidant in biofortified wheat have been worked out which was in order of black > blue > purple > white (Kumari et al., 2020). Antioxidant is mainly present in wheat which is transferred via chapatti and it does not get degraded.

NUTRITIONAL SECURITY VERSES FOOD SECURITY IN SOCIETY

As per WHO program bio-fortification wheat can give a nutritional security to Indian citizen by undermining impact of increasing malnutrition in children and pregnant women's. Earlier food hunger was an issue so Indian Government has launched a program for Food Security to reduce hunger index. As per Global perspective India's current hunger Index is around 110 (2021) and therefore, has launched several program such as Midday Meal Scheme (MMS), Integrated Child Development Services scheme (ICDSS) and the Public Distribution System (PDS) under National Food Security Act, in 2013 with mission to provide for food and nutritional security to poor people at affordable prices.

Now with more data, nutritional security has been defined more accurately such as bio fortified cereal grains specially wheat, rice and other crops like maize (Aziz et al., 2019; Cormick et al., 2020; Murphy & Westmark, 2020; Wang, Kong, Liu, Fan, & Zhang, 2020). According to a report PM Kalyan Yojana around 1.74 Crore was spent to provide Covid-19, effected poor people to overcome the economic impact. Extended effort done by Government in form of providing concept of multi nutria-farm where fortified cereal grain is permitted to grow with increased content of protein and micronutrients, namely vitamins and minerals to provide sufficient nutrition to malnourished children's (Alvi & Gupta, 2020).

Anthocyanins are water soluble pigments that belong to class flavonoids in which white wheat contains more phenolic acid as antioxidants. Comparatively therefore, total phenolic acid and antioxidant content (134>122>120>13 in total anthocyanin test TAC) enhanced in order of color such as black>blue>purple>white (S. Sharma et al., 2018).

Major thiamine storage compartment of wheat or rice, the aleurone, is removed during refinement. For this reason, refined wheat flour and polished rice are common foods fortified with thiamin. The Food and Drug Administration of the United States (FDA) mandates that refined wheat flour be enriched with 2.9 mg thiamine per pound flour (FDA, 2018), and 66 total countries have fortification programs in place for wheat flour, maize flour, and/or rice (GFDx, 2019).

Fig 1. Source cited Comparative vitamins Daily requirements verses available in wheat (Garg et al., 2021)

	micronutrition	DR (mg/kg)	after fortification
1	Vitamin A	1	..12
2	Vitamin B1	4.4	0.12
3	Vitamin B2	2.6	0.04
4	Vitamin B3	35	1.25
5	Folic acid 1.0	1	0.04
6	Vitamin B 12	0.008	0.004
7	Iron	15	29
8	Zinc	30	27

Grain Zn content in wheat improved from 28.96 to 36.61 mg·kg⁻¹ and that in flour increased from 10.51 to 14.82 mg·kg⁻¹ after Zn fortification (Wang et al., 2020).

Zinc wheat

Grain Zn content in wheat was 31.84 mg·kg⁻¹ globally but varied across continents, for example, 25.10 mg·kg⁻¹ in Europe, 29.00 mg·kg⁻¹ in Africa, 33.63 mg·kg⁻¹ in Asia, and 33.91 mg·kg⁻¹ in North America. Grain Zn content in wheat improved from 28.96 to 36.61 mg·kg⁻¹ and that in

flour increased from 10.51 to 14.82 mg·kg⁻¹ after Zn fortification.

Furthermore, Zn content varied in the different processed components of wheat; that is, Zn content was 12.58 mg·kg⁻¹ in flour, 70.49 mg·kg⁻¹ in shorts, and 86.45 mg·kg⁻¹ in bran. Zinc content was also different in wheat-derived foods, such as 13.65 mg·kg⁻¹ in baked food, 10.65 mg·kg⁻¹ in fried food, and 8.03 mg·kg⁻¹ in cooking food. Therefore, the suitable Zn fortification, appropriate processing, and food type of wheat are important to meet people's Zn requirement through wheat. (Wang et al., 2020).

1. WHO. Recommendations on wheat and maize flour fortification: meeting report - interim consensus statement. Geneva, World Health Organization; 2009 (http://www.who.int/nutrition/publications/micronutrient/s/wheat_maize_fortification/en/).

Table 2.

Vitamin	Physiologic roles	Deficiency
Thiamin (B₁)	Co-enzyme functions in metabolism of carbohydrates and branched-chain amino acids	Beri-beri, polyneuritis, and Wernicke-Korsakoff syndrome
Riboflavin (B₂)	Co-enzyme functions in numerous oxidation and reduction reactions	Growth, cheilosis, angular stomatitis, and dermatitis
Niacin (nicotinic acid and nicotinamide)	Co-substrate/co-enzyme for hydrogen transfer with numerous dehydrogenases	Pellagra with diarrhoea, dermatitis, and dementia
Vitamin B₆ (pyridoxine, pyridoxamine, and pyridoxal)	Co-enzyme functions in metabolism of amino acids, glycogen, and sphingoid bases	Naso-lateral seborrhoea, glossitis, and peripheral neuropathy (epileptiform convulsions in infants)
Pantothenic acid	Constituent of co-enzyme A and phosphopantetheine involved in fatty acid metabolism	Fatigue, sleep disturbances, impaired coordination, and nausea
Biotin	Co-enzyme functions in bicarbonate-dependent carboxylations	Fatigue, depression, nausea, dermatitis, and muscular pains

2. FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization), IFAD (International Fund for Agricultural Development), WFP (World Food Program). The State of Food Insecurity in the World 2015. Meeting the 2015 International Hunger Targets: Taking Stock of Uneven Progress. Rome: FAO; 2015.

One of the best wheat rich in anthocyanin is purple wheat now started to be grown in various part of India and other countries. In Mohali Punjab by scientist (Beleggia et al., 2021; Francavilla & Joye, 2020; Hirawan, Diehl-Jones, & Beta, 2011; Paznocht et al., 2018; S. Sharma et al., 2018).

There was production of double bio fortification product rich in both Zinc and iron and was

reported to be high as compared to wheat (S. Sharma et al., 2018).

A new variety of Bio-fortified bread wheat variety developed and named as HI 1633 (Pusa Vani), have been developed by the Indian Agricultural Research Institute, Regional Station, ICAR- Indore.

Bio-fortified bread wheat variety with yield 47 q/h-1 and can be grown late and also has been characterized for best quality of bread and biscuit while micronutrient reported was around 41 ppm of both iron and zinc (Sai Prasad et al., 2021).

In removing malnutrition

Bio-fortification is the process of enriching the staple food crops with nutrients and a way towards more nourishing future. ZINC deficiency generally caused 48.1 per cent among under five years children in Uttar Pradesh (Tewari, Rani, Singh, Singh, & Singh, 2017). In combating malnutrition such bio-fortification is highly required achieve the goal of nutritional security in Uttar Pradesh as well as India. (Tewari et al., 2017). **Bio-fortified coloured wheat are known for their anthocyanin content** (N. Sharma et al., 2022). Black and blue wheat flour and chapatti samples had higher total amino acid content, and nutrition index in comparison other flour and chapatti samples, while EAA content were similar among all flour and chapatti samples. After chapatti cooking, average percent reduction in amino acid content in black, blue, purple and white wheat were 11.41, 12.4, 19.0, and 23.8%, respectively. White chapatti samples exhibited >20% losses in the contents of 14 amino acids, while black chapatti showed >20% losses in case of only (N. Sharma et al., 2022). The higher retention of amino acids in coloured wheat might be due to the masking and protective effects of anthocyanin's on proteins and amino acids from heating and oxidative damages.

Conclusion

As per vision 2030 main aim is to provide nutrition rich food to poor lactating mothers and undemourished children's (Jose, Gulati, & Khurana, 2020). In Indian scenario trend is changing where people are now more aware of growing food organically. Large famers in Punjab growing fortified wheat such as purple wheat.

Affordability may be an issue because price are high of these products as per reports 63–76% of the rural poor could not afford a recommended diet in 2011 (Ragunathan, Headey, & Herforth, 2021). Some authors believe that Millet can be one of the good alternative to that area where it's difficult to grow cereals such as draught affected (Brahmachari, Sarkar, Santra, & Maitra, 2019). Backyard poultry farming is also suggested as one of the best alternative in rural families with improved income and nutrition (M. Kumar, Dahiya, & Ratwan, 2021).

The fortification done via two methods 1) Agronomic method 2) Genetic engineering Bio fortification methods.

Breeding method or GE methods can increase the availability and efficiency of micronutrients like Iron and Zinc.

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